

Synthesis and fast atom bombardment mass spectrometry of mixed ligand complexes $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})\text{L}_2$

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Manuscript received 19 April 2007, accepted 10 May 2007

Abstract : Mixed ligand complexes of the type $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})\text{L}_2]$ (where acacH = acetylacetone and HL = salicylaldehyde, 5-bromo-(5-chloro- or 5-nitro-)salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone, benzoylacetone or dibenzoylmethane) have been synthesized by the reactions of $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3$ with the corresponding carbonyl compounds in 1 : 2 molar ratios. These complexes have been characterized by IR, electronic, ESR and fast atom bombardment mass spectrometry. They exhibit less intense molecular ion $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})\text{L}_2]^+$ peaks, however, very strong peak due to the fragment $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})^+$ is observed. Peaks due to other fragments e.g. $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_2^+$, CrL_2^+ , $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})\text{L}^+$ are also observed. Oligomeric species such as $\text{Cr}_2(\text{acac})_3^+$ and $\text{Cr}_2(\text{acac})_4^+$ are also formed.

Keywords : Mixed ligand complexes, chromium(III), β -diketone.

Mixed ligand complexes of Cr^{III} with acetylacetone or substituted acetylacetone and N-containing ligands have been reported¹⁻⁴. Mass spectral studies of acetylacetonates and substituted acetylacetonates of Cr^{III} and other metals have been carried out⁵⁻⁹. However, the mass spectra of mixed ligand complexes of Cr^{III} with β -diketones and other ligands have not been reported so far. We have carried out the reactions of $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3$ with various carbonyl compounds, which result in the formation of mixed ligand complexes $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})\text{L}_2]$ (**1a-f** and **2a,b**). Fast atom bombardment mass spectra of these complexes have been recorded and the results are described in the present paper.

Results and discussion

The reactions of $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3$ with salicylaldehyde, 5-bromo-(5-chloro- or 5-nitro-)salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone, benzoylacetone or dibenzoylmethane in 1 : 2 molar ratios have yielded mixed ligand complexes of the type $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})\text{L}_2]$. These complexes are brown solids and are insoluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, nitrobenzene and methanol but soluble in DMF. The analyses and characteristics of the complexes are recorded in Table 1. The conductances of the complexes are very low (2-9 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) indicating their non-electrolytic nature¹⁰. The μ_{eff} values of the complexes at 302 K are in the range 3.97-4.16 B.M. These values are in accordance with the

	R	X
(a)	H	H
(b)	H	Br
(c)	H	Cl
(d)	H	NO_2
(e)	CH_3	H
(f)	C_2H_5	H

(1)

high spin d^3 configuration of Cr^{III} suggesting octahedral geometry around the metal atom.

Infrared spectra :

The IR spectra of Cr^{III} mixed ligand complexes exhibit strong absorption bands in the region 1570-1650 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to coordinated $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$. In

free acetylacetonate and benzoylacetonate the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ band has been reported at 1724 cm^{-1} ¹¹ and in 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ band appears at 1680 cm^{-1} . Graddon and coworkers reported $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ absorption bands for free salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone, acetylacetonate and benzoyl-

acetone at 1680 , 1660 , 1650 , 1724 and 1724 cm^{-1} respectively¹². Thus the shifting of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ to lower wave number side in the mixed ligand complexes supports the chelation of these ligands to the metal atom. Such shifts to lower wave number side on complexation have been reported in case of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} acetylacetonates^{13,14}. Bands in the region $1450\text{--}1560\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the mixed ligand complexes of Cr^{III} may be assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$. Strong to medium intensity absorption bands in the region $400\text{--}600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which are not present in the free ligands may be attributed to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ vibrations¹⁵. Pinchas *et al.*¹⁶ studied various ¹⁸O labeled acetylacetonates of Cr^{III} and assigned bands at 1520 cm^{-1} to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$, at 1570 cm^{-1} to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and at $415\text{--}660\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ vibrations.

Electronic spectra :

In the electronic spectra of Cr^{III} complexes three bands are observed at $250\text{--}350$, $350\text{--}450$ and $500\text{--}600\text{ nm}$ which can be assigned to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) transitions respectively.

Table 1. Analyses and characteristics of mixed ligand complexes of Cr^{III}

Sl. no.	Complex Molecular formula Mol. Wt.	Colour and decomp. temp. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) :			Molar conductances ($\Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
				Metal	C	H		
1.	[Cr(acac)(sal) ₂] C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₆ Cr 393.33	Brown (264)	37	13.36 (13.21)	58.16 (58.01)	4.26 (4.35)	2	3.97
2.	[Cr(acac)(hap) ₂] C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₆ Cr 421.38	Brown (272)	54	12.23 (12.33)	59.46 (59.85)	5.13 (5.02)	4	4.07
3.	[Cr(acac)(hpp) ₂] C ₂₃ H ₂₅ O ₆ Cr 449.44	Brown (278)	47	11.89 (11.56)	61.23 (61.46)	5.77 (5.60)	2	4.04
4.	[Cr(acac)(5-Brsal) ₂] C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₆ Br ₂ Cr 551.12	Brown (242)	33	9.78 (9.43)	41.51 (41.40)	2.66 (2.74)	7	4.16
5.	[Cr(acac)(5-Clsal) ₂] C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₆ Cl ₂ Cr 462.40	Brown (252)	45	11.50 (11.24)	60.46 (60.34)	4.93 (4.89)	5	4.09
6.	[Cr(acac)(5-NO ₂ sal) ₂] C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₁₀ N ₂ Cr 483.45	Brown (328)	37	10.56 (10.75)	47.32 (47.20)	3.04 (3.12)	9	3.99
7.	[Cr(acac)(bzac) ₂] C ₂₅ H ₂₅ O ₆ Cr 473.46	Brown (262)	36	11.09 (10.98)	63.54 (63.42)	5.41 (5.32)	5	3.98
8.	[Cr(acac)(dbzm) ₂] C ₃₅ H ₂₉ O ₆ Cr 597.60	Brown (212)	32	8.90 (8.70)	70.21 (70.34)	4.75 (4.89)	3	3.98

Lintvedt and Kernitsky have assigned the bands at 550–600 nm to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (F) transitions in substituted tris(acetylacetonates) of chromium¹⁷. Fatta and Lintvedt studied a series of β -diketonates of Cr^{III} and assigned the bands at 350–450 and 550–600 nm to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (F) (ν_2) and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (F) (ν_1) transitions respectively¹⁸. The values of the ratio ν_2/ν_1 (~ 1.4) suggest distorted octahedral geometry around Cr^{III} . Various ligand field parameters have been calculated for Cr^{III} complexes. The value of first spin allowed transition (ν_1) at $\sim 17000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is directly taken as $10 Dq$. The value of Racah inter-electronic repulsion parameter (B) can be calculated by the equation of Underhill and Billing¹⁹.

$$B = (\nu_3 + \nu_2 - 30 Dq)/15$$

The calculated values of B are $\sim 550 \pm 100$ (Table 2). These values were compared against the value (918 cm^{-1}) for the free Cr^{III} ion, which indicates considerable covalent character of the metal-ligand bonds in these complexes with the covalency factor (β_{35} for spin allowed transitions) varying in the range 0.6 ± 0.1 .

ClSal_2] (**1c**), $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})(\text{hpp})_2]$ (**1f**) and $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})(\text{dbzm})_2]$ (**2b**) have been recorded. The m/z values of the peaks along with their intensities relative to the base peak are given in Table 3. Mass spectrum of $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})(\text{dbzm})_2]$ is reproduced in Fig. 1. Peaks at m/z 136, 137, 154, 289 and 307 are due to NBA matrix. All the complexes exhibit molecular ion (M^+) peaks of low intensities **1c** (m/z 462, 2.6%), **1f** (m/z 449, 2.0%) and **2b** (m/z 597, 7.9%). Sasaki and coworkers⁵ have studied the mass spectra of various metal acetylacetonates and have observed that for the central metal atoms having electronegativities between 1.6–1.8, molecular ion peak was of very low intensity or was not observed. Removal of one ligand (L) from the molecular ion gives $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})\text{L}^+$ which gives less intense peak in complex **1f** (m/z 300, 5.2%) while an intense peak is observed in the complexes **1c** (m/z 306, 23.7%) and **2b** (m/z 374, 84.2%). In all the three complexes a strong peak is observed at m/z 151 (**1c**, 47.3%; **1f**, 44.7%; **2b**, 31.6%) due to $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})^+$ which could be formed by the loss of two molecules of the other ligands from the molecular ion (M^+). In all the complexes of

Table 2. Electronic spectral data of mixed ligand complexes of Cr^{III}

Complex	Transition (cm^{-1})			$10 Dq$ (cm^{-1})	B (cm^{-1})	β_{35}	(ν_2/ν_1)
	${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$	${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$	${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$				
	(ν_1)	(ν_2)	(ν_3)				
$[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})(\text{sal})_2]$	17669	25316	35670	17669	525	0.57	1.43
$[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})(\text{hap})_2]$	17543	25000	35420	17543	519	0.56	1.42
$[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})(\text{hpp})_2]$	17857	25974	36100	17857	567	0.61	1.45
$[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})(5\text{-Brsal})_2]$	17543	25125	37037	17543	635	0.69	1.43
$[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})(5\text{-ClSal})_2]$	17981	25641	36496	17981	546	0.59	1.42
$[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})(5\text{-NO}_2\text{sal})_2]$	17543	25641	35445	17543	564	0.61	1.46
$[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})(\text{bzac})_2]$	18018	25316	36240	18018	500	0.54	1.40
$[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})(\text{dbzm})_2]$	17857	25641	36080	17857	543	0.59	1.43

ESR spectra :

The ESR spectrum of one representative complex $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})(\text{hap})_2]$ has been recorded. The spectrum shows two signals both of strong intensity with $g_{\parallel} = 2.0251$ and $g_{\perp} = 3.9598$. The g_{iso} value calculated from g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} comes out to be 1.9949. These values are consistent with an octahedral structure around Cr^{III} . For the complex $[\text{Cr}(\text{LH})(\text{L}'\text{H})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$ (where L = uracil and L' = histidine). Narang and coworkers²⁰ have reported g_{iso} value 1.914 at room temperature suggesting octahedral geometry around Cr^{III} .

FAB mass spectra :

FAB mass spectra of three complexes $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})(5-$

Table 3. Mass spectral data of mixed ligand complexes of Cr^{III} (m/z values and relative abundances)

Ion	$\text{Cr}(\text{acac})(\text{hpp})_2$	$\text{Cr}(\text{acac})(5\text{-ClSal})_2$	$\text{Cr}(\text{acac})(\text{dbzm})_2$
$[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})\text{L}_2^+]$ (M^+)	449 (2.0%)	462 (2.6%)	597 (7.9%)
$\text{Cr}(\text{acac})^+$	151 (44.7%)	151 (47.3%)	151 (31.6%)
CrL^+	201 (2.6%)	207 (2.6%)	275 (13.1%)
$\text{Cr}(\text{acac})\frac{1}{2}$	250 (100%)	250 (100%)	250 (100%)
CrL_2^+	350 (36.8%)	362 (5.3%)	498 (23.7%)
$\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_2\text{L}^+$	399 (2.6%)	405 (23.7%)	473 (21.0%)
$\text{Cr}(\text{acac})\text{L}^+$	300 (5.2%)	306 (23.7%)	374 (84.2%)
$\text{Cr}_2(\text{acac})\frac{1}{2}$	401 (11.4%)	401 (18.4%)	401 (2.6%)
$\text{Cr}_2(\text{acac})\frac{1}{4}$	500 (14.0%)	500 (15.8%)	500 (2.6%)

L = hpp, 5-ClSal or dbzm.

Fig. 1. FAB mass spectrum of [Cr(acac)(dbzm)₂].

Cr^{III} the base peak is observed at *m/z* 250 due to the species Cr(acac)₂⁺ formation of which can be explained by the following equation :

Cr(acac)₃ has also been reported to give base peak at *m/z* 250 due to Cr(acac)₂⁺^{13,14}. Similarly, the base peak due to Cr(acacX)₂⁺ has been reported in the mass spectra of Cr(acacX)₃ (where X = Cl, Br, I).

All the three complexes exhibit a peak due to Cr(acac)₂L⁺ (**1c**, *m/z* 405, 23.7%; **1f**, *m/z* 399, 2.6% and **2b**, *m/z* 473, 21.0%), formation of which can be explained by the following equation :

All the complexes show a peak corresponding to CrL₂⁺ (**1c**, *m/z* 362, 5.3%; **1f**, *m/z*, 350, 36.8% and **2b**, *m/z* 498, 23.7%). Formation of CrL⁺ ion is evidenced by the appearance of a peak in **1c** at (*m/z* 207, 2.6%), **1f** at (*m/z* 201, 2.6%) and in **2b** at (*m/z* 275, 13.1%). Formation of CrL₂⁺ and CrL⁺ can be explained by the following equation :

Presence of peaks due to various oligomeric species can be explained with the help of the following reactions :

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone and 2-hydroxypropiofenone were purified by distillation. 5-Bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde, 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde, benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane were purified by recrystallization from hot ethanol. Ethanol was distilled before use. Chromium was determined volumetrically by potassium dichromate using diphenylamine as indicator. Specific conductances were measured in DMF at room temperature (30 °C) by a Systronics direct reading conductivity meter-304. IR spectra (KBr) of the complexes were recorded in the region 400–4000 cm⁻¹ on a Shimadzu-8400 S spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded in DMF on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda-15 spectrophotometer in the range 200–850 nm. Magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature (30°C) on a Gouy balance using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as a calibrant. The FAB mass spectra of the complexes were recorded at CDRI, Lucknow on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/Data system using Argon/Xenon (6 Kv, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The ESR spectrum was recorded at SAIF, IIT Madras using Varian E-112 spectrometer.

Synthesis of the complexes :

To an ethanolic solution of Cr(acac)₃ (4.57 mmol,

1.597 g in 10 ml), 2-hydroxypropiophenone (9.15 mmol, 1.374 g in 10 ml of ethanol) was added with stirring. A clear brown solution was obtained. The pH of the reaction mixture was ~3.0. After stirring for half an hour it was refluxed for 20 h. The solid complex [Cr(acac)(hpp)₂] which was separated was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similarly, the reactions of Cr(acac)₃ with salicylaldehyde, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde, 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane were carried out in 1 : 2 molar ratios to give corresponding mixed ligand complexes.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the UGC, New Delhi for financial support, the Head, Chemistry Department, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur for laboratory facilities, the Head, Chemistry Department, Banasthali Vidyapith, Banasthali (Rajasthan) for magnetic measurements and the Director, CDRI, Lucknow for C, H analyses and FAB mass spectra and the Head, SAIF, IIT Madras for ESR spectra.

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